

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Notes

2.1 Work Session Guidelines

COHESIVE

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date	1-2 July 2019
Venue	FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment Eurostation II, Place Victor Horta / Victor Hortaplein, 40 box 10 1060 Brussels, Belgium. Across exit of train station Brussel- Zuid/Bruxelles-midi
Meeting	COHESIVE task 2.1 Work Session Development of guidelines for national One Health structures
Room	Day 1: Peyo 01C234 Day 2: Vandersteen 01C220
Contact	Frank Koenen: +32473730849 Kitty Maassen: +31650438206

Above, from left to right: Gaia Scavia, Karin Nyberg, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Stephen Wyllie, Elina Lahti, Frank Koenen

Below, from left to right: Marieke Timmer, Valérie de Waele, Rosangela Tozzoli, Kitty Maassen, Sandra Cavaco

Not on the picture unfortunately: Victor Del Rio Vilas

Participants	Email-address
Solveig Jore, Norway (sick)	solveig.jore@fhi.no
Gaia Scavia, Italy	gaia.scavia@iss.it
Rosangela Tozzoli, Italy	rosangela.tozzoli@iss.it
Marieke Timmer, The Netherlands	Marieke.timmer@rivm.nl
Sandra Cavaco, Portugal	sandra.cavaco@iniav.pt
Victor Del Rio Vilas, U.K. (only July 1st)	vdelriovilas@yahoo.co.uk
Kitty Maassen, The Netherlands	Kitty.Maassen@rivm.nl
Mathilde Uiterwijk, The Netherlands (notes)	Mathilde.Uiterwijk@rivm.nl
Valérie de Waele, Belgium	Valerie.DeWaele@sciensano.be
Frank Koenen, Belgium	Frank.Koenen@sciensano.be
Stephen Wyllie, U.K.	stephen.wyllie@apha.gov.uk
Elina Lahti, Sweden	Elina.lahti@sva.se
Karin Nyberg, Sweden	Karin.nyberg@slv.se

One Health EJP Cohesive
 WP2.1 Development of guidelines hosted by Sciensano, Brussel, Belgium

July 1-2 2019

Day	Time	
Monday July 1	9.00-9.15	Walk in & coffee/tea
	9.15-9.45	Welcome & introduction of the participants & goal of the work session
	9.45-10.15	Results focus group
	10.15-10.30	Coffee/tea
	10.30-11.00	Creative warming up exercise
	11.00-12.30	Structuring the Guidelines, part I
	12.30-13.30	Lunch
	13.30-15.00	Structuring the Guidelines, part II
	15.00-15.15	Coffee/tea
	15.15-17.30	Structuring the Guidelines, part III
	19.30-	Diner at Bonsoir (Clara Dansaertlaan, Brussel)

Tuesday July 2	9.00-10.15	Refine the results of Monday
	10.15-10.30	Coffee/tea
	10.30-11.00	Warming up exercise
	11.00-12.30	Content of the Guidelines, part I
	12.30-13.30	Lunch
	13.30-15.00	Content of the Guidelines, part I
	15.00-15.15	Coffee/tea break
	15.15-17.00	Logistics and follow-up

N.B. Below are the notes I made of the session, these are not minutes (Mathilde)

The entire work session was recorded for analysis and mood impression (that will be without sound) and will be destroyed after the analysis has been performed

PROGRAMME:

Day 1. After the introduction by Kitty (see ppt 20190701 OHEJP Cohesive WP2.1 Brussel), we started with a creative warm up session. Each participant was asked to write down the recipe for pasta Bolognese (which the Italian don't know in this fashion, as it turned out, but call ragù Bolognese ;-))

By discussing each other recipes and ingredients, it became clear that there are many different approaches but also similarities and ingredients that were crucial. (and we got hold of two original Italian recipes ☺).

This is a metaphor for the Guidelines, in a way, because ingredients and the steps to follow can be either crucial or nice-to-add/nice-to-have. Keeping this principle in mind, we started in two-pairs to discuss and write down how a zoonosis (or one health?) structure should look like (ingredients & pathways) -> see pdf Notes_groups_Guidelines work session_Bruxelles pages 5-10.

We then discussed this during a plenary session, in which a basic structure was drafted -> see below of JPEG Flipover_boxes OH guideline_Brussel July 2019

Day 2. Marieke had prepared another creative session -> visual thinking (for more information, see this webinar about Visual Thinking <https://vimeo.com/233447174>. And a book tip: Visual thinking, Willemien Brand). The idea is to visualize the ideas, in order to make them more attractive and comprehensible. A definition: a way to organize your thoughts and improve your ability to think and communicate. It's a great way to convey complex or potentially confusing information.

*One Health EJP Cohesive
WP2.1 Development of guidelines hosted by Sciensano, Brussel, Belgium*

July 1-2 2019

To practice, we were first asked to draw our pasta Bolognese recipe.

Then, with the creative part of our brain warmed up, we each tried to visualize zoonosis/OH structure -> see pdf Drawings_OH_creative part_Guidelines work session_Bruxelles

We also discussed again the structure we drafted on Day 1. Two aspects of that structure were further analysed, using the Brainwriting method. This means that one starts to write relevant information about the subject or answer to the question on a paper, and passes it on to the next participant, who can add to the previous comment or add something new -> see pdf Notes_groups_Guidelines work session_Bruxelles pages 1-4. When everybody had contributed, the comments are discussed in a plenary session to further analyse, smooth and organise the ideas. See below or the JPEGs Flipover_joint risk assessment_OH Guidelines_Brussel_July 2019 and Flipover_coordinated risk management_OH Guidelines_Brussel_July 2019

The flipovers were afterwards typed out and further structured, see below.

NOTES:

Important questions that were (partly) discussed during the meeting, but need to be specified in detail:

WHAT IS THE AIM OF THE GUIDELINE?

WHAT IS THE AIM OF THE STRUCTURE?

FIRST, WE NEED TO DECIDE UPON THE TARGET AUDIENCE

SHOULD THE GUIDELINES BE TO CREATE ZOOONOSIS STRUCTURE OR ONE HEALTH STRUCTURE?

STRUCTURE OR SYSTEM?

Types of action:

- Reactive -> sharing signals. Be on the safe side; bring it in, also if there's doubt whether it's relevant
Definition: not signal, but 'Information that might lead to a signal'
- Proactive planning; scenario analysis (option)

Such as consequences of brain drain (especially in some European countries); anticipate on that proactively by drafting scenario analyses. Define in the terms of reference which risks, who can bring subjects for scenario analysis in.

Describe reactive forms, but also the options of performing proactive work (take it a step further); for example analysis of vector-borne diseases when a vector enters/establishes

Cascade of failures, introduction of a rabies positive dog -> preparedness & capacity plan (contingency plan) -> systems thinking (tracking systems instead of events)

Harmonisation of data (comparable data) gathering is important.

Risks -> prevent, mitigate (reduce) control, or externalise

Risk communication -> coordinated, one core message, different focus, transparent and understandable

Not only scientific compounds, but also taking the general public into account

Monitoring & evaluation is an important component throughout the entire scheme

Transparency on the process. For example, be transparent about the information gaps, such as data from private or foreign labs which are not shared, for whatever reason, usually.

Basics -> e.g. political will, capacity, resources, such as lab resources, good (enough) level of diagnostics, knowledge, trust, enabling legislation, cost effectiveness, equality, robust human & veterinary health system

Barriers -> e.g. corruption, lack of awareness, refusal to share data, legal restraints

Preparedness -> essential in the backbone? Optional to include it in the structure? Some kind of preparedness is necessary anyway. Sustain the OH structure processes. Training personnel, creating awareness, lab resources, diagnostics

Contingency plans -> flexibility to use the existing plans to use for (re) emerging events, make them work better within the OH-structure

Terms of reference -> very important to start with, for each group (for example to describe responsibilities of the joint risk assessment group and the risk management group). Include confidentiality and sharing information and results. Possibly, share data but this is not necessary (there are commercial and privacy constraints); at least share information derived from this data. Data will be good for strategic joint documents, scenario planning, retrospective analyses, etc. For outbreak and urgent situations sharing information is sufficient.

Opinions of persons do not need to be made publically -> put that in the minutes. Make signals publically, keep opinions private. What level of recommendations and advice to describe in the r.a. Set up the terms of reference with specific disciplines, such as legal advice, communication

Good practice examples ->

- Control for Salmonella in U.K. There was very much resistance against it. Now they perceive it as a benefit for the U.K. poultry sector ('our eggs/meat are Salmonella free!')

Terms & definitions:

-> see European Regulations

- One Health
- Signal: an observation in humans and/or animals with public health relevance that will be checked for the need for further action (such as risk assessment or communication to professionals) -> from the questionnaire

- Joint risk assessment (JRA)
- Risk assessment -> reactive form, after a signal, has some kind of status, advice formulated to risk managers (ideally from all of the relevant sectors) -> coordinated risk management
- Feasibility assessment -> with the relevant stakeholders (if industry is involved, not at an early stage, to prevent increasing the difficulty of decision making. So, they are not involved in the decision making, but can share their opinions)
- Risk management -> risk communication, control measures

EU general risk assessment methodology (Action 5 of Multi-Annual Action Plan for the surveillance of products in the EU (COM(2013)76): https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=4&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjG_oWL4pPjAhX_wAIHHRIJCREQFjADegQIAxAC&url=https%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2Fdocsroom%2Fdocuments%2F17107%2Fattachments%2F1%2Ftranslations%2Fen%2Frenditions%2Fpdf&usg=AOvVaw2UjTzC7kHk4KUpjY7u5Xlf

Definition from this action plan: the process of identifying, selecting and implementing measures that can be applied to reduce the level of risk.

Taking responsibility

- Control
- Preparedness = food safety definition of FAO: A process used in advance of a potential zoonotic disease event to ensure that capacity and resources will be available to respond.

<http://www.fao.org/3/ca2942en/ca2942en.pdf>

For Cohesive, is also applicable for Animal health & public health

- Draagvlak (a very Dutch word ;-)) ~ gain acceptance, public or general support

Guidelines:

- Easy to find
- Visual attractive
- Short
- “modular” or “live”? Deliver a product that initially satisfies the main demand but that allows “enhancements”. In a way, we’d be replicating many products out there in the market that generate a “captive” customer base by regularly delivering updates. (comment of Victor)

Governmental board:

- High level persons
- Important for example when risk assessment for policy makers is performed
- Might help to get political will and money. Bring ministries together.

- They perform strategic planning, can support actions, but are not involved in the actual actions
- In more complex countries where money has to come from several resources, a governmental board might help a lot
- For some countries, multiple governmental boards at different levels (ministries, regional)
- Opportunity to establish a wider and more powerful body. Representatives from the regional level in the central body.
- Can already existing bodies perform as such? Or need to establish new bodies?
- Generalists needed to combine the results of the joint risk assessments in the different OH structures -> to define common risks and possible solutions

Joint Risk Assessment

- Independent practical scientist -> involve industry?? Define pros and cons of involving them
- Meet physically, at a regular basis
- Allow fresh blood, assure that's not going to be a 'fossil' group
- Coordinated risk management can ask the question to the jra group, or the jra group can start because a signal/event/threat was detected in the zoonosis structure

The advisory board (relevant Stakeholders; policy makers, industry etc) including the risk management group -> consultation of feasibility, cost effectiveness etc of the control measures

Barrier of the visibility of the risk management is institutes on regional level, with no overarching institutes

Implementation guideline ->

OH risk analysis structure -> operational

Content

Review: let the concept be reviewed by

- Public health representatives
- Risk managers

Division of work:

Meeting November 27-29 in Rome, in the centre. Not necessary to present deliveries then for 2.1

Start early Wednesday till Friday.

Combine wp2 & wp3, also a larger Stakeholder Meeting

*One Health EJP Cohesive
WP2.1 Development of guidelines hosted by Sciensano, Brussel, Belgium*

July 1-2 2019

Possible satellite meeting (Tuesday) horizon scanning exercise. Task 2.1 worksession starts also Tuesday afternoon

Draft implementation Guide by the end of the year -> meeting necessary earlier than November -> beginning of October, with homework done.

Set out Date planner, for 1,5 days, combination with 3.1 meeting (1/2 day). Location: Schiphol, London Weybridge.

Lay-out of the Guidelines:

- Visual
- Basic framework; goal etc
- Click through/links where additional information, tips and tricks, tools etc can be found
- Short booklet

Work that can be done now: -> make a first draft of the proceedings of the first work session

- Type it out, structure, logical order -> subjects on the flip-overs
 - Frank, Valérie -> joint risk assessment -> see COHESIVE_WP2_JointRiskAssessment_20190711_FK VdW Javeira Rebolledo Gonzalez KM

- Elina, Karin -> coordinated risk management -> see Cohesive -coordinated risk management_Karin Elina

- Kitty, Marieke, Mathilde -> structure -> see INGREDIENTS ZONOSIS_MU KM and Notes INGREDIENTS zoonosis structure_MU KM

Sent back to the group, before July 15

VC week of July 15 (Wednesday 17 for example) Date planner

- Gather content & write descriptive text

One Health EJP Cohesive
 WP2.1 Development of guidelines hosted by Sciensano, Brussel, Belgium

July 1-2 2019

Is it a Guideline for Zoonosis structure or OH structure? Guideline will be generic any way. Too early to decide upon that. The pilots will help with deciding

What might to be added at a later stage:

- Advice, tips, tools
- Best practices, do's and don't's (lessons learned), experiences
- Chapters/paragraphs
- Methods/tools for getting the discussion going, hosting work sessions, conducting exercises, etcetera

Keep in mind that we need to have in mind why there's a need for another OH guidelines besides the TZG of FAO/WHO/OIE

- Attractive and more practical tips, more dynamic
- Be used as training material by EU
- Who is the target of the TZG and who is our target? Ours is for the medium and basic level of enthusiastic workers who feel at a daily basis that something OH needs to be constructed
- Describe the area in between the r.a. and the risk management ('the grey area')
- Implementation part -> how to construct a OH structure, at any level, at national or regional level

Idea to repeat the work session during the pilot (for example Italy), or the system thinking approach -> discuss further during the October meeting

Additional interesting information & papers

Kindly shared by Victor

1. A ppt briefly describing UNDRR Global Risk Assessment Framework (GRAF) and they systems thinking approach -> see Cohesive_July19_GRAF_Victor

2. A paper about vulnerability assessments. You will remember I brought out this challenge for the guidelines. On this issue, I would like to stress that the UNDRR states that the development and implementation of vulnerability assess. is still a huge challenge: <http://www.ajtmh.org/docserver/fulltext/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0327/tpmd180327.pdf?expires=1562143073&id=id&acname=quest&checksum=53E38579E616DB487ACB0D90C7D0B342>

3. A nice editorial about one of the papers above: <http://www.ajtmh.org/docserver/fulltext/10.4269/ajtmh.19-0354/tpmd190354.pdf?expires=1562146496&id=id&acname=quest&checksum=2EAA0F7E49F142B92D46F9C5A7C6B806>

4. A couple of papers showing the relevance of integrating animal and public health surveillance data, and how this informs risk estimates with more precision.

4.1. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6034302/>

4.2. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1877584517301752>

5. A mechanism developed and implemented while I was in Defra to prioritise emerging threats to the UK, still, to the best of my knowledge, in use 10 years after its launch: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167587712002681?via%3Dihub>